

IMPACT OF SMALL BUSINESSES AND BUSINESS ENTITIES IN UZBEKISTAN ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECONOMY

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Abstract

The number of small businesses and micro-firms has been increasing in the economy of Uzbekistan in recent years. This sector plays an important role in economic growth, employment, innovation and competitiveness. Small businesses, in particular, contribute to the sustainability of local communities by creating economic opportunities. In this article, you can see an analysis of how the increase in the number of small businesses in Uzbekistan affects the economy. Entrepreneurs play an important role in bringing new innovations and market development beyond average jobs. Innovations created by business entities and their impact on the economy are studied during the research. The impact of business entities on the economy is of great importance in the current global economic environment. The influence and role of business entities operating in the field of industry, services and innovations in Uzbekistan on the economy is analyzed.

Key words: Small business, business entities, population employment, emergence of new small enterprises and microfirms, Gross domestic product (GDP) Import, export, service, trade.

Introduction

Small business and private entrepreneurship are important in the development of local and national economies by contributing to employment, innovation and economic growth in the development of the economy. This study is dedicated to analyzing the impact of the increase in the number of small businesses on the economy.

"The impact of business entities on the economy is one of the most widely read topics. The impact of entrepreneurial activity on the economy is widely linked through the innovative approach of enterprises and businesses, financial

development and job creation."("Impact of business entities on the economy" - Abdulazizov N.B. 2021)

"Entrepreneurship has a critical importance for bringing development and reform in the economy. Business entities have a notable impact on the economy by establishing financial development, job creation, and innovation."("The impact of entrepreneurship on the economy and its essence" - Kadyrov O.O. 2020)

"Business entities are the main component of the country's economy. They empower the economy through the establishment of innovation, the creation of new jobs, and financial development."("Entrepreneurial activity and its impact on the economy" - Nazarov F.R. 2022)

Methodology

In the coverage of the article, our legislation aimed at the development of small and private business entities, decrees and decisions of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, scientific works of famous scientists were studied and analyzed the role of small and private entrepreneurship in the economy. At the same time, methods such as logical and comparative methods of analysis, analysis and synthesis, systematic approach, regression analysis, economic-statistical analysis, sample observation, and experiment were used in the study of subject-specific statistics and theories in the research process. Textbooks, teaching aids, foreign literature, Periodical Press, scientific and practical and international conference collections, as well as internet information were used to cover the topic.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The number of small business and private business entities in the Republic of Uzbekistan has increased from 23,697 in 2003 to 35,104 in 2023, and this has

recorded an increase above 48% in the twenty years (diagram 1).

Diagram 1. The number of business entities in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2003-2023 (pcs.)¹.

In the same years, the country's GDP grew from Rs 9,884 crore to Rs 1,066,569 crore. This in turn shows an increase of 10,734% (diagram 2).

Diagram 2. GDP indicators in the Republic of Uzbekistan between 2003 and 2023 (crore) .

Measures to activate entrepreneurship have served the emergence of new small enterprises and microfirms, and most importantly, the creation of new jobs, the share of small enterprises in the gross domestic product is increasing every year. As can be seen in Figure 1 below, Small Business share in gross

¹ Prepared by the author on the basis of the data of the Statistical Agency under the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan

domestic product is 54%, small business share in industry sector is 32.8%, forest and fisheries is 97.5%, and trade is 85%.

Figure 1. The role of small businesses in Gross domestic product (GDP).²

We can also see the great impact of the growth of business entities in countries on population employment (diagram 3). Including the population of business entities in 2003 of nearly 9,589,000, this indicator reached 13,706,000 by 2022. The increase in this range is 42.9%.

Diagram 3. Number of employees in business entities.³

² Prepared by the author on the basis of the data of the Statistical Agency under the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan

³ Prepared by the author on the basis of the data of the Statistical Agency under the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	23
Model	2.0672e+12	1	2.0672e+12	F(1, 21)	=	840.87
Residual	5.1626e+10	21	2.4584e+09	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9756
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9745
Total	2.1188e+12	22	9.6309e+10	Root MSE	=	49582

YaIMmlrd	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Faolfirmalar	2.326549	.0802319	29.00	0.000	2.159697 2.4934
_cons	-329756.3	22706.26	-14.52	0.000	-376976.5 -282536

Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
-329756.3	22706.26	-14.52	0.000	-376976.5 -282536
2.326549	.0802319	29.00	0.000	2.159697 2.4934

Figure 2. Relationship between business entities and GDP⁴.

These results of regression analysis provide the following information for the economy of Uzbekistan:

- F- the high value of his statistics and Prob > F too low a value, means that the analyzed model is statistically very strong. That is, it is clear and reliable that the model depends on the growth of the number of business entities.

R-Square (R²):

- R² the value is very high (0.9756), this shows that a large part of the changes in GDP is explained by the model through an increase in the number of business entities. That is, when the number of business entities increases, almost all of the changes observed in GDP are explained by this increase.

In the regression coefficient, each unit increase of the subjects of the rejection increases the GDP by about 2.326549 million (if the unit is a million). Since the standard error is very low, this analysis is much more accurate and reliable.

- Constant coefficient (intercept) -329756.3 the negative value of indicates that if the number of business entities is equal to zero, the expected low level of GDP value can be, this situation can be theoretically and practically ambiguous, since GDP does not depend only on the number of business entities.

- The quoted 95% confidence interval for coefficients indicates the exact limits of the impact of the number of business entities on GDP. For example, the

⁴Stata@15 calculated by the author using the program

increase in GDP for each business entity can range from 2.159697 million to 2.4934 million.

The results of the study showed that in addition to the increase in the number of small businesses, the number of jobs also increased significantly. Also, small businesses are active in producing new products and services that encourage innovation. Indicators of economic growth have also shown positive dynamics, confirming the positive impact of small businesses on the economy.

According to the results of the analysis, the increase in the number of small businesses significantly increased the level of economic activity and employment in Uzbekistan. Small businesses were primarily active in the service, agricultural and manufacturing sectors, encouraging innovation and competitiveness in these areas. Tax revenue analysis shows that the small business sector contributed to the expansion of the tax base. Also, small businesses are helping to increase the competitiveness of Uzbekistan's products in domestic and international markets.

The increase in the number of small businesses has a positive effect on the economy of Uzbekistan, but there are still many difficulties for the further development of this sector. For example, access to financial resources, lack of skilled labor, and improvement of the regulatory framework are important. It is also necessary to develop a policy of support for small businesses, to create the necessary conditions to ensure their stability and increase export potential.

Discussing among scientists about the impact of business entities on the economy, according to their instructions, the impact of entrepreneurial activity on the economy is enormous. Some scientists believe that entrepreneurial activity leads to the creation of new jobs, innovation, market development. Other scholars argue that entrepreneurial activity provides opportunities to empower the economy by increasing income, increasing jobs, and motivating participants. In general, business entities have a huge impact on the economy through innovation, job creation and income growth.

Paul Gompers and Josh Lerner: they have described the impact of business entities on the economy with empirical examples that support it. For example, they have studied the impact of startup companies on the economy by bringing innovation and creating new jobs.

William Baumol: he discussed the "entrepreneurial model" in showing the impact of business entities on the economy, and gave examples in his articles on what forms of giving power to the economy is conducted by increasing the income of entrepreneurship, creating work and bringing innovation.

We also agree with the opinion of researchers. Business entities really play an important role in the growth of the economy.

Conclusion

The increase in the number of small businesses in Uzbekistan is an important factor for economic growth, employment and innovation. The development of this sector helps to increase competitiveness in various sectors of the economy and strengthen the position of Uzbekistan in local and international markets. Cooperation between the public and private sectors, as well as improving the entrepreneurial environment, ensures more sustainable development of small businesses. The significance of the article is also evident from regression analysis.

Prob > F the fact that the value is too low means that the analyzed model is statistically very strong. It is possible to know that the square value of R is very high that is, it is 0.9756, since we can see that when the number of business entities increases, GDP affects kata. The regression coefficient determined that the growth of business entities per unit increases to 2.3 million dollars per GDP. At the same time, we can see the level of dependence of GDP on business entities as 95% reliability.

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